

ISic1479

I.Sicily inscription 1479

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.01.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Camarina

Place of origin (modern)

Kamarina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico

Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331204

1. Κλεινοῦς.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644989

EDCS 70900789

PHI 331204

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0939

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 113 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Cordano, F. 1984. Camarina VII: alcuni documenti iscritti importanti per la storia della città. *Bolletino d'Arte*. Anno 69 vol 26: 31-56. At 32 fig.3

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